

ANALYSIS OF SOUTH AFRICA'S AGRICULTURE INDUSTRY COMPETITIVENESS IN SACU

Singuwa Chimuka

PhD Assistant Lecturer and a scholar in International Relations affiliated with the Department of Theory and History of International Relations at the Peoples' Friendship University of Russia (RUDN University)

Daniel Kumafan Terzungwe

second-year Master's student in International Relations at the Department of Theory and History of International Relations,

Peoples' Friendship University of Russia

Singuwa Gospel

fourth-year Political Science student in the Department of Comparative Political Science at Peoples' Friendship University of Russia (RUDN University)

Abstract

Considering regional integration in Southern Africa, there is no better place than the Southern African Customs (SACU), the world's oldest customs union. There is no better industry to examine than the vital agriculture industry in SACU. Agriculture contributes more than 10% in Lesotho, Namibia, and Eswatini and less in Botswana and South Africa. For this reason, the research work focuses on analyzing South Africa's agriculture industry competitiveness advantage in SACU. *Methodologically*, the paper applied Porter's Diamond Model to understand the factors that give South Africa's agriculture industry a competitive advantage in the Southern African Customs Union. The author concludes that not all SACU countries are predominantly agriculture-driven economies. South Africa has substantial and diversified manufacturing capacity, but its agriculture industry needs a competitive advantage in the SACU. However, the country is an agricultural products net exporter within the SACU market. In other words, agriculture's relative contribution is overshadowed by the manufacturing and mining industries, thus reducing the chance of being competitive within the SACU market.

Keywords: South Africa, SACU, Porters Diamond model, Trade, Agriculture.

INTRODUCTION

Trade liberalization and attending globalization have led to governments evaluating their competitive advantage in global markets. Competitive advantage is necessary for long-term sustainability of the agriculture industry; therefore, businesses along a value chain must position themselves to be competitive in the world market. South Africa is part of the global economy following deregulation in the mid-1990s, which implies that the economy faces fierce competition in international markets.

The country has regarded the sub-region of Southern Africa as one of its most vital foreign relations priorities. This is shown by its commitment to all spheres of the Southern African Customs Union (SACU) agenda, including the promotion of conditions for fair competition in the Customs area, enhancing the economic development of the member states, and promoting the integration of the member states into the global economy through trade and investment initiatives.

The Republic of South Africa (RSA) is an upper-middle-income country of 57 million people. It is one of the African continent's most advanced and diverse economies. It has a well-developed business market and is a gateway to markets in sub-Saharan Africa. The country is an attractive business destination due to its growing demand and well-developed infrastructure capable of efficiently distributing imported and local agricultural products to major urban centers and the entire southern African region.

South Africa's economy is the second largest in Africa after Nigeria. Moreover, it is one of the most industrialized countries in Africa. Since 1996 and after more than twelve years of international sanctions arising

from the apartheid regime, South Africa's gross domestic product has almost tripled, peaking at \$807 billion in 2022.

The agriculture industry's contribution to the South African economy has always been vital, direct, and indirect. The role that agriculture plays was, and will always be, increasing the food supply for domestic consumption, releasing labour for industrial employment, enlarging the market for industrial output, increasing the supply of domestic savings, and earning foreign exchange through agricultural exports, as a result of these reasons, the industry needs to be kept updated and competitive.

The SACU, in the spirit of a customs union, provides for the free flow of agricultural products among member states. However, it has been noted that decisions on the customs tariff were dictated by South African industrial policy. It is often recognized that a similar situation has applied concerning agricultural policy in SACU. To prove this wrong, the theory of competitive advantage, in combination with Porter's diamond model, has been used in many industries in South Africa [7]. This study focuses on the competitive advantage of the South African agriculture industry in the SACU market. The study will put much emphasis on the past two decades.

THE CONCEPT OF COMPETITIVENESS IN THE CONTEXT OF INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTIVITY

The term competitiveness has become one of the central preoccupations of industry or nation but could be more enigmatic in the definition. Michael Porter stated that, in looking at competitiveness, the analysis should assess productivity. In other words, countries

contend for market share in the world economy, contesting foreign investment and export sales through their business [16].

Industrialization is necessary for the developing countries of SACU to increase the member states growth. The intention is to improve a country's regional and international competitiveness in a specific industry to meet product demand in the global market. For a country to be competitive, all surrounding factors need to support each other and have the ability to identify any obstacles to economic growth [3]. However, some studies have argued that it is impossible to identify the barriers to a country's economic growth since the challenges can manifest in several ways, such as the accumulation of fixed capital, labour productivity, and physical infrastructure, amongst many other enabling factors to competitiveness [20].

Just as productivity impacts the competitiveness of a country or the industry, it is also a fundamental element for increasing the companies' competitiveness. Competition, in general, influences the business environment, both in the definition of strategies, objectives, and goals of the organization, as well as in structuring resources necessary to execute internal processes dynamically and efficiently. Thus, a competitive company can deliver products and services effectively, with prices and quality appropriate to its consumer [10].

Thus, companies continually seek ways to adapt to economic, social, political, technological, and structural changes, that is, to environmental changes. As a consequence of these changes, organizations face situations of uncertainty and are exposed to a series of threats and opportunities, which influence the choice of strategies, the definition of objectives, and the decision-making process [6].

Competitiveness is determined by the nation's productivity (value per input unit) using human, capital, and natural resources. Below are some of the critical moments for a country's competitiveness, thus:

- Productivity sets the standard of living that a nation can sustain.
- Productivity depends on the prices that a country's products and services command, not just on efficiency, for instance, uniqueness and quality.
- It is different from what industries a country competes in that matters for economic growth but how it competes in those industries.
- Productivity requires a combination of domestic and foreign firms operating in the country.
- The productivity of domestic industries is fundamental to competitiveness, not just that of traded industries.

There are traditional ways of measuring a country's competitiveness. Using the multi-factor evaluation method thus, the Porter's Diamond model developed by Michael Porter in 1990 identifies four main components and includes two features that analyze why specific industries were competitive in certain locations.

THE PORTERS DIAMOND MODEL (1990)

Michael Porter designed the Diamond model in his book "The competitiveness of nations." in a diversion from his traditional organizational-based research, Porter designed this model with industries as his analysis unit. He stated that only a few nations were truly internationally competitive. According to Michael Porter, the critical determinants of national competitiveness are the four endogenous factors, thus factor condition, demand condition, related and supporting industries, firm strategy, structure, and rivalry- and two exogenous factors – chance and government [12].

These industries were not singular firms but clusters of firms and all participants in the broader industry. The main point identified in the book was the implications of geographical concentration within which each industry and that competitive industries tended to be located in particular areas. **The model is geographically represented in Figure 1**

(Source: Michael Porter -The Competitiveness of nations)

Porter's diamond model shows a mutually reinforcing system. **Factor Conditions** are the presence of factors for production. Contrary to conventional wisdom, Porter argues that "key" factors of production (or specialized factors) are created, not inherited. Specialized factors of production are skilled labour, capital, and infrastructure. "Non-key" or common factors, such as unskilled labour and raw materials, can be acquired by any company and therefore do not create a sustainable competitive advantage. Specialized factors, however, involve significant, sustained investment. Therefore, they are difficult to duplicate. This creates a competitive advantage because if other firms cannot easily duplicate these factors, they are valuable. For example, Japan has built a competitive global economic presence beyond the country's resources, partly by producing many engineers who have helped spur technological innovation in Japanese industry.

Demand conditions relate to the size and nature of the product's customer base, thus the domestic market, which also drives product innovation and improvement. Larger and more dynamic consumer markets will demand and drive the need to differentiate, innovate, and increase the market scale for businesses [4]. If customers are very demanding, firms are constantly pressured to improve their competitiveness through innovative products, high quality, etc.

Related supporting industries refer to upstream and downstream industries that foster innovation through exchanging information and promote the continuous exchange of ideas. They can drive innovation depending on the degree of transparency and knowledge transfer [16]. The related supporting industries in the Diamond model correspond to suppliers and customers that may pose threats or opportunities in the Five Forces model.

Firm strategy, structure, and rivalry refer to the basic fact that competition leads firms to find ways to increase production and develop technological innovation [17]. The concentration of market power, the degree of competition, and the ability of competing firms to enter the national market are essential here. This point relates to competitive forces and barriers to new market entrants in the five forces model.

Porter also suggests that the primary role of government in stimulating a country's economy is to encourage domestic businesses to focus on creating and developing elements of the factor environment. One way for the government to achieve this goal is to encourage competition among domestic companies by enacting and enforcing antitrust laws. The chance factor can play a role in the success or failure of a firm with a competitive advantage in the market since it is beyond the control of the country. For instance, unpredictable events like wars, natural disasters, political situations, etc., can positively or negatively impact an industry or nation, creating a competitive advantage or wiping it off [7].

PORTER'S DETERMINANTS OF COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE IN THE SOUTH AFRICAN AGRICULTURE INDUSTRY

Agriculture plays a dominant role in the economies of SACU countries. Member States have agreed

to cooperate on agricultural policies to ensure the coordinated development of the agriculture industry within the customs union area. The SACU agricultural policy will focus on, among other things promoting environmentally sustainable rural livelihoods, sustainable resource management, and more equitable access to resources and services for farming communities. The objective would be to ensure a stable/sustained source of income for the agricultural community, thereby reducing rural poverty. Such a strategy will improve investor confidence and will attract investment (both domestic and foreign) into agriculture-related activities and rural areas.

SACU Member States have agreed that there shall be competition policies in each Member State and co-operation concerning enforcing competition laws and regulations. However, the SACU has often been criticized as a trade agreement benefiting its most significant and most powerful member, South Africa, and detrimental to its smaller members by hindering industrialization and inducing trade diversion, thus giving South Africa a competitive advantage in different industries, such as the agriculture industry.

The competitive advantage of the South African agriculture industry is not determined by one factor. Factors to look at include the value of the Rand, productivity, market strategy, advances in information and technology, trade, local sales, consumer preferences, research and development, firm strategy, and government support.

The factor conditions are generally deemed constraining by South African agriculture industry decision-makers. Most factors are regarded as constraining, with the most constraining being Input cost. Input cost has always been regarded as a constraining factor in most agricultural studies done in South African agriculture [8]. The main reason is that most inputs used in South African agriculture are imported, and input costs become prohibitive due to a weak Rand value [9]. Other constraining factors include the cost of infrastructure and access to natural resources – due to droughts, natural resources like water have become constraining in recent years. In addition, the cost of skilled and unskilled labour is deemed constraining – due to minimum wages set by the government (minimum wage for farm workers is R25,42 per hour, which equates to approximately 1.41 USD). However, the quality of infrastructure, quality of technology, and availability of unskilled labour are considered enhancing factors of the South African agriculture industry compared to other SACU members.

In addition, a basic factor such as land is considered enhancing factor for South Africa's agriculture industry competitiveness within the SACU region. This is because South Africa has the largest agricultural land on the African continent. As of 2020, the country's agricultural land amounted to over 96 million hectares, representing almost 80 percent of the total land area. Of those, around 87 percent were classified as land under permanent meadows and pastures, while nearly 12.5 percent of the agricultural land was arable land.

Agricultural land in South Africa from 2000 to 2020 (in 1,000 hectares)

Source: www.statista.com

During the period reviewed, the area used for the cultivation of crops and the production of animals generally decreased until 2011, then stayed stable.

South African agricultural demand conditions are an enhancing factor for the demand conditions. All factors of demand conditions can be considered enhancing factors. Due to the health benefits related to agricultural products, there is no surprise that demand conditions are considered enhancing. The size of the lo-

cal and international market for South African agricultural products is considered large enough to accommodate the industry's production. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in SACU was estimated at R6.8 trillion in 2021, from R6.0 trillion recorded in 2020. The economy grew by 5.1 percent after contracting at a pace of 6.4 percent recorded in 2020. The table 1 below shows the GDP at Current Prices (in South African Rand) by Member States

Table 1

GDP at Current Prices (in ZAR) by Member States

Member States/Period	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Botswana	230 184	231 843	246 718	265 284	246 640	278 415
Eswatini	56 132	58 689	61 771	64 615	65 432	70 123
Lesotho	31 354	30 727	33 272	34 188	34 856	35 076
Namibia	157 708	171 570	181 009	181 234	174 827	181 935
South Africa	4 359 061	4 653 579	4 873 899	5 077 625	5 521 075	6 192 497
SACU	4 834 438	5 146 408	5 396 669	5 622 946	6 042 830	6 758 045

Source: Statistics Office in the Member States (National Accounts), and Secretariat computation

However, compared with the other SACU members, South Africa has one of the low GDP growth rates

(%) in 2021 - Botswana, 11.8%, Eswatini 7.9 %, Lesotho, 1.6, Namibia 2.7%, and South Africa, 4.9%.

GDP growth rates (%)

GDP growth rates (%) ¹						
Member States/Period	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Botswana	4.3	2.9	4.5	3.0	-4.8	11.8
Eswatini	1.1	2.0	2.4	2.2	-1.9	7.9
Lesotho	3.6	-3.2	-1.2	-0.4	-6.5	1.6
Namibia	0.0	-1.0	1.1	-1.6	-8.5	2.7
South Africa	0.4	1.4	0.8	0.2	1.5	4.9
SACU (weighted average)	0.6	1.4	1.0	0.2	-6.4	5.1

Source: Statistics Office in the Member States (National Accounts), and Secretariat computation.

Additionally, contribution to GDP by Economic Activity (agriculture) at Current Prices in 2022 (%), Botswana 1.8%, Eswatini 8.1%, Lesotho 4.2%, Namibia 9.5%, and South Africa 2.5%. Table 3 shows the contribution to GDP by Economic Activity in the year

2021(%). Although South Africa has a large amount of agricultural land, it is not as productive as other countries, and the agriculture industry is not as important to the economy as other industries.

Table 2

Contribution to GDP by Economic Activity in the year 2021(%).

Economic Activity	Botswana	Eswatini	Lesotho	Namibia	South Africa
Agriculture, Hunting, forestry and fishing	1.8	8.1	4.2	9.5	2.5
Mining and quarrying	15.8	0.2	5.1	9.1	7.7
Manufacturing	5.2	26.7	16.6	11.3	11.8
Electricity, gas and water supply	1.1	2.6	4.7	3.1	2.8
Construction	10.9	2.9	2.1	1.8	2.3
Wholesale, retail trade, hotel and restaurants ²	12.4	14.9	7.5	12.0	12.1
Transport, storage and Communications	4.5	6.2	4.4	4.5	6.4
Financial intermediation & Business Services	10.0	12.4	15.7	13.0	21.3
Other activities ³	33.4	19.0	27.4	28.8	23.1
Taxes less subsidies on products	4.9	7.0	12.2	6.9	10.0
GDP at market prices	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Statistics Office in the Member States (National Accounts), and Secretariat computation.

By economic activity, Mining and Quarrying were among the significant contributors to the economy in Botswana (15.8%), while in Eswatini and Lesotho, the Manufacturing industry was among the key contributing industries. In Namibia and South Africa, Financial and Business services are ranked among the key contributing industries.

For the related and supporting industries, Porter argues that the presence of internationally competitive related or supporting industries increases an industry's competitive advantage in that these companies provide products or services efficiently and effectively, and in most cases- they provide these products or services cost-effectively. Related and Supporting industries factors are generally considered enhancing.

The South African agricultural input industry is well-developed and represented in the SACU region. It

consists of the following sectors: equipment, including machinery and implements, fertilizer, seeds, and chemicals which make the industry more competitive.

The equipment industry: South Africa has only small agricultural machinery and implements manufacturing industry, with most equipment and machinery being imported. The tractors manufactured in South Africa annually represent only about 5% of the total. However, the industry has experienced a positive trend in tractor and combined sales, except for balers. This can mainly be attributed to the exceptionally high prices of maize, wheat, and sunflower that allowed the farmer to replace old machines. On the positive side, if the Rand remains stable at current levels, lower input costs may encourage farmers to invest, making the South Africa Agriculture industry more competitive in SACU.

The manufacturing of tractors in South Africa, as one of the most critical agricultural machines used by crop farmers, is not very competitive in the international arena but gives the country a competitive advantage in the SACU region because of a definite positive trend in competitiveness over the long-run and short-run [19].

Fertiliser – increasingly competitive in the region: South African fertilizer manufacturers are more competitive in the Southern Africa Customs Union. Fertiliser manufacturers have a positive trend in international competitiveness in the long run and have also had one for the past ten years.

Pesticides – marginal with positive trends: Pesticide manufacturers in South Africa are relatively marginally competitive internationally. Pesticide manufacturers, however, have a positive tendency to competitiveness in the long and short term.

In South Africa, rapid population growth and increasing economic prosperity continue to create immediate demand for the agricultural sector. It was estimated that the population of South Africa will reach 82

million by 2035. With the increasing population, the demand for food is projected to double in the coming years. The country's demand for fruits and vegetables is further driven by increasing income, rapid urbanization, and a shift in consumers' diet preferences toward nutritional food. As a result, the food consumption rates in the country are rising almost 5-6 times faster than the local production. In 2018, fruits and vegetables accounted for 16% of the total food products consumed in the country, and the demand for off-season fruits is usually met through rising imports.

The increasing need for food security within a booming population and greater demand from a rising middle-class population for food is driving the growth of the agriculture sector in the country. The rise in imports reflected an increase in demand for fruits and vegetables. Therefore, the increasing demand for food crops due to the rising population in the country, especially for fruits and vegetables, is anticipated to drive the market during the forecast period.

Agriculture in South Africa: Population in million, South Africa, 2017-2020

Source: World Bank

South African food crops dominate the agricultural market in the region. Maize is the most essential food crop, followed by wheat and barley. South Africa reported 10.51 million metric tons of maize production in 2018/2019, with an accessible state province accounting for 38.7% of the total maize production in South Africa. In January 2017, the area of cultivation for maize increased by 33%, owing to good rainfall. Climatic conditions, coupled with a need for more knowledge about transfer activities, are the major limitation to the agriculture sector in South Africa. Government initiatives like the creation of Agri-parks and the

introduction of projects like Project Khulisa are expected to promote the cultivation of food crops in the country. Favorable climatic conditions and supportive government policies are expected to drive the South African agriculture market. Maize accounts for more than 80% of the local food crop production in South Africa. The South African food crop market has matured considerably since the deregulation of marketing. Producers, traders, and other intermediaries interact freely in marketing their produce.

Agriculture in South Africa: Production in thousand metric ton, Cereals, South Africa 2017-2027

Source: World Bank

In Addition, the recent most worrying factor is electricity supply; not only is the supply not enough,

but the cost of electricity has also been increasing since 2008. Electricity prices in South Africa have

dramatically outpaced inflation over the past decade (ever since the 2008 electricity supply shortage crisis). Over ten years, Eskom's electricity prices have increased by about 356%, while inflation over the same

period was 74%. This means that electricity prices have increased four times faster than inflation. Currently, taxes on electricity keeps on rising with power cuts [14].

Source: Eskom, Stats SA, Absa Research

Firm strategy, structure, and rivalry highlight organizational systems to a more significant extent [15]. Porter indicates that no one organizational system is universally appropriate for all firms. Still, a competitive advantage of industries results from management practices, and Firm strategy, structure, and rivalry factors for agricultural products are considered enhancing. Management of competition in the international market, management of competition in the local market, and management of market intelligence are all considered to be enhanced by experts [2]. However, some things could be improved in the willingness to invest agriculture industry, which can be highlighted as one of the most constraining factors. This is highly linked to

the land reform debate in South Africa. Therefore, confidence in investing in agriculture generally is currently low. However, the South African agriculture products market has matured considerably since the deregulation of marketing. Producers, traders, and other intermediaries interact freely in marketing their produce. The South African government also gives the farmers freedom to choose the market where they want to trade their products. Hence, if the farmers do not get desirable production prices, they can sell their commodities in the international market. Despite the substantial fluctuations in cereal production over the study period, cereal production is expected to grow at a nominal growth rate, mainly owing to government policies favoring sustainable cereal production in the country.

Source: statista

The South African agriculture industry produces a wide variety of crops. In terms of agricultural production, in 2020, sugar cane and maize were the leading crops in the country, with 18.2 million and 15.3 million metric tons, respectively. In addition, corn plays a significant role in the agriculture industry in South Africa. In 2020, the agricultural crop covered the largest harvested land area. Additionally, the country was among the ten-leading corn-producing nations worldwide as of 2021/2022. In 2020, there were more than 179 million chickens in South Africa. Sheep and cattle followed, however, with a significantly lower volume of 21.6 million and 12.3 million heads, respectively. As of the same year, animals and animal products generated an income of 152 billion South African rands (8.75 billion U.S. dollars).

When analyzing the Government support and policy of firms or industry, Porter noted two opposing views on the role of government in improving compet-

itive advantage. On the one hand, some economists argue that government should support the marketplace through targeted policies such as subsidies, price support, etc. On the other hand, argue for limited government involvement. Porter, however, argues that both these notions of government involvement are wrong and states that the role of government should be to act as a catalyst to push companies to higher levels of competition. In the case of South Africa, the influence of government policies constrains competitive agricultural advantage. – the most constraining Porter’s determinant factor. All factors related to government support and policy are considered constraining, with the credibility of the political system, labor policy, and land reform policy considered the most constricting. Foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows into South Africa have been low, albeit on a rising trend. Regarding industrial distribution, FDI inflows are channeled mainly to mining and quarrying, manufacturing, particularly the clothing industry, and finance and services [11].

South Africa Foreign Direct Investment 1970-2023

Data Source: World Bank

Porter describes chance factors as factors that companies or industries have no control over; industry decision-makers can only try to manage them to enhance their competitive advantage [1]. Chance factors have a constraining effect on the South African agriculture industry's competitive advantage in SACU. There are many factors impacting on the industry – including credit ratings downgrade, land reform concerns, volatile exchange rate, ongoing weather concerns and the latest Covid-19 pandemic. In addition, unfavourable weather has played a crucial role in the South African agriculture industry in the past few years, with droughts being the main topic.

Export diversification contributes to a country's economic resilience, especially in the face of disruptions to global supply chains or if one of the major markets imposes non-tariff barriers to protect its producers from competition, as it is increasingly the case. An example of South Africa's vulnerability to a lack of diversification was illustrated recently by two events. China temporarily banned imports of South African wool and the EU restricted imports. This mattered because outside the African continent, South Africa's agricultural exports are heavily concentrated in a few Asian countries and the EU.

CONCLUSION

The commodity agriculture industry in South Africa is very diversified and self-sufficient in most staple foods, except wheat, rice, chicken meat, and oilseeds. In addition, South Africa has a well-developed agribusiness industry, which is essential for job creation and economic development. The Republic of South Africa is SACU's leading exporter of agricultural products, primarily citrus fruits, wine, fruit, and maize.

In 2022, South Africa's agricultural exports reached US\$12.8 billion, up 4% from the previous year. Imports, nevertheless, remain significant, averaging US\$6.6 billion over the past five years. Major exports included fresh oranges, grapes, wine, and maize, excluding seed maize, fresh apples, wool, fresh or dried lemons and limes, fresh pears, mandarins, and prepared food products. The cereals industry is one of the largest agriculture industries in the country, accounting for more than 30% of the total gross value of agricultural production. The industries comprises several key stakeholders, including raw material suppliers, farmers, granary owners, traders, flour millers, bakers, research organizations, financiers, etc.

However, the South African agriculture industry is uncompetitive in the SACU market even if the country dominates the customs union economically. In the last decade, the South African agriculture industry has been a net exporter of the agriculture industry. However, the exported quantities need to be higher for the industry to be considered competitive than the Agricultural Indicators of the SACU Countries.

In Porter's model analysis, the most critical factors that are found to have enhancing factors are industries are demand conditions, firm strategy, and rivalry and related and supporting industries, respectively. On the other hand, the main factors that constrict competitive advantage are the cost of inputs, the credibility of the political system, and labour and land policy. Therefore,

the Agriculture industry needs to capitalize on enhancing factors and manage constricting factors to improve its competitive advantage in the SACU market and be sustainable in the long run.

South Africa's agriculture industry is export oriented. Thus, any improvements in production through various development plans, such as the Agriculture and Argo-processing Master Plan, should be anchored on expanding export markets. Japan, China, India, Saudi Arabia, Bangladesh, the Philippines, and South Korea are key markets in which South African agribusinesses and farmers are interested in expanding their presence. It's also important to maintain a relationship with the existing key markets. All this should happen while domestic efforts to improve the functioning of the network industries are under way. This will be the only realistic path to maintaining the growth of this industry and, with that, job creation and vibrancy of the rural towns.

References

1. Портер М., Кетелс К. Конкурентоспособность на распутье: направления развития российской экономики / Отчет Центра стратегических разработок. М.: ЦСР, 2007.
2. Дюмулен И.И. Международная торговля. Экономика, политика, практика. -М.: ВАВТ Минэкономразвития России, 2015. - 464с.
3. Шимко П. Д. Международная экономика: учебник для академического бакалавриата / П. Д. Шимко, Н. И. Диденко; под ред. П. Д. Шимко. — М.: Юрайт, 2014. — 752 с.
4. Aiginger K., & Vogel J. 2015. Competitiveness: From a misleading concept to a strategy supporting Beyond GDP goals // *Competitiveness Review*, 25(5): P. 502.
5. Boonzaaier, J.D.L. (2015). An inquiry into the competitiveness of the South African stone fruit industry. Unpublished master's thesis. Stellenbosch: Stellenbosch University.
6. Buckley PJ, Pass CL, Prescott K. Measures of international competitiveness: A critical survey. *J Mark Manag.* 1988;4(2):175-200.
7. Cho D.-S., Moon H.C. Does one size fit all A dual double diamond approach to country-specific advantages / *Asian Business & Management*, 2009, Vol. 8, 1, PP. 83-102.
8. Dlikilili, X. (2018). An analysis of the competitive performance of the South African citrus industry. Unpublished master's thesis. Stellenbosch: Stellenbosch University.
9. Esterhuizen, D., van Rooyen, C.J. & van Zyl, J. (2001). The competitiveness of the agricultural input industry in South Africa. *Agrekon*, 40: 678 – 684.
10. Hu W, Wall G. Environmental Management, Environmental Image and the Competitive Tourist Attraction. *J Sustain Tour.* 2005; 13(6):617-35.
11. Henok, W. and Kaulihowa, T. (2022), "The impact of FDI on human capital development in SACU countries", *International Journal of Social Economics*, Vol. 49 No. 2, pp. 268-279.
12. Lee, H. (2019). An analysis of foreign direct investment attractiveness of the Russian Far East by

Porter's Diamond model. ResearchGate.2019-3-334-340.

13. Moon H.C., Rugman A.M., Verbeke, A. A generalized double diamond approach to the global competitiveness of Korea and Singapore / *International Business Review*, 1998, 7, PP. 135-150.

14. Ndou, P. (2012). The competitiveness of the South African citrus industry in the face of the changing global health and environmental standards. Unpublished PhD dissertation. Alice: University of Fort Hare.

15. Porter, M. E. (1990). The competitive advantage of nations. *Harvard Business Review*, 68: 73-91.

16. Porter M.E. Clusters and the new economics of competition. *Harvard Business Review*, 1998, 76 (6). PP. 77-90.

17. Porter M.E. What is strategy? / *Harvard Business Review*, 1996, 74 (6). PP. 61-78.

18. Robert Kirk and Matthew Stern, "The New Southern African Customs Union Agreement," *The World Economy* 28, no. 2 (2005): 171.

19. Smit, A. 2010. The competitive advantage of nations: Is Porter's diamond framework a new theory that explains the international competitiveness of countries? *Southern African Business Review*, 14(1): 105-130.

20. Vera, L. (2013). Some useful concepts for development economics in the tradition of Latin American structuralism. *American Journal of Economics and Sociology*, 72(4), 917-948.